

Treatment stability of valproate, carbamazepine, and levetiracetam: a therapeutic drug monitoring study

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Abstract

This study evaluated treatment stability—defined as the maintenance of therapeutic serum concentrations—of antiepileptic drugs in patients undergoing long-term therapy, with emphasis on the role of therapeutic drug monitoring in optimizing pharmacotherapy. A retrospective analysis of 78 patients at the University Hospital in Nitra (2020–2022) examined serum drug concentrations and treatment stability for valproate, carbamazepine, and levetiracetam. Psychiatric diagnoses were highly prevalent among patients using valproate (93.18%) and carbamazepine (61.10%), whereas levetiracetam was primarily prescribed for neurological conditions (60%). The proportion of patients with therapeutic serum concentrations increased from the first to the second measurement for all drugs, with carbamazepine demonstrating the most substantial improvement (66.7% to 100%). Treatment stability was highest among patients receiving carbamazepine (66.7%), compared to those on valproate (34.1%) and levetiracetam (31.3%). Outpatient status and carbamazepine use were significantly associated with greater treatment stability, underscoring the importance of patient setting and drug selection in optimizing antiepileptic therapy.

Keywords

carbamazepine, drug monitoring, levetiracetam, serum concentration, valproic acid

Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 50 million people worldwide suffer from epilepsy, with over 6 million affected individuals in Europe (Cross 2011; WHO 2024). In Slovakia, nearly 60,000 patients with diagnoses G40.0–G41.9 were recorded in 2023, and 13,733 new cases were diagnosed in the same year, according to the National Health Information Centre (NCZI 2022). The primary goal of appropriately selected

antiepileptic therapy is to achieve complete seizure control (Gunasekera et al. 2023), thereby enabling patients to engage fully in daily activities without compromise to cognitive or physical functioning.

In addition to their use in the treatment of epilepsy, antiepileptic drugs (AEDs) are also used in the management of various psychiatric and neurological disorders, such as migraine (Bagnato and Good 2016), neuropathic pain (Wiffen et al. 2013), affective disorders, and schizophrenia (Druschky et al. 2018). AEDs may also be beneficial in patients

with a history of alcohol abuse, particularly in the prevention and treatment of alcohol withdrawal syndrome (Hammond et al. 2015). The mechanisms of action of AEDs relevant to their use in psychiatric disorders involve modulation of GABAergic inhibition and reduction of glutamatergic excitation, both of which are considered relevant to the pathophysiology of these conditions (Puranen et al. 2023).

The initiation of antiepileptic treatment requires careful selection of the most suitable agent, or a combination thereof, accompanied by stepwise dose titration to establish an individualized and effective maintenance dose (Tomson et al. 2023). The effectiveness of epilepsy treatment is affected by several factors, particularly age, genetic background, and the presence of comorbid conditions, all of which impact the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of AEDs (Iapadre et al. 2018).

Therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM) of AEDs is most beneficial during treatment initiation, after dose adjustments, in cases of suspected drug interactions or treatment failure, as well as in cases of overdose or clinical signs of toxicity. The primary aim of TDM is not only to minimize the risk of seizures and adverse drug reactions but also to optimize pharmacotherapy and define reference serum or plasma concentration ranges for each drug (Patsalos et al. 2018). Samples for TDM should be collected once a steady state has been achieved, which typically occurs after approximately 4 to 5 biological half-lives following the initiation or adjustment of therapy. In the case of AEDs with a short half-life, such as carbamazepine, valproate, or levetiracetam, it is recommended to collect the sample immediately prior to the next scheduled dose (Grundmann and Kacířová 2016).

Maintaining stable serum concentrations of AEDs presents a significant clinical challenge due to factors such as individual variability in metabolism (Johannessen Landmark et al. 2012), concomitant therapy and drug interactions (Spoelhof et al. 2017), and inconsistent medication intake (Jopowicz et al. 2024). In this context, the primary aim of our study was to evaluate treatment stability—defined as maintaining serum drug levels within the therapeutic range throughout the monitoring period—by analyzing and comparing the serum concentrations of three commonly used AEDs (valproate, carbamazepine, and levetiracetam) in patients undergoing long-term therapy. Our goal was to better understand the factors influencing optimal seizure control and treatment persistence. Notably, to our knowledge, this is the first study in the Slovak Republic to systematically address AED therapy stability, particularly given that therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM) has not yet been widely implemented as routine practice across all hospitals in Slovakia.

Methods

Patient selection and sample size calculation

This retrospective study was conducted at the University Hospital in Nitra, Slovak Republic. Patient data were col-

lected by a pharmacist and fully anonymized in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR); no identifiable information was included in the analysis.

The sample size was calculated based on the number of patients who had serum concentrations of the monitored antiepileptic drugs determined at the University Hospital in Nitra between 2020 and 2022, totaling 2,331 patients. Using a 90% confidence interval and a 10% margin of error, the calculated sample size was 66 patients (Raosoft, Inc. 2004). Ultimately, 78 patients were included, exceeding the calculated minimum to increase statistical power, improve the reliability and generalizability of the findings, account for potential data variability or loss, and enable robust subgroup and multivariable analyses.

Data were obtained from laboratory request forms for patients who underwent two serum concentration measurements of valproate, carbamazepine, or levetiracetam between 2020 and 2022. Inclusion criteria were long-term administration (>3 months) of one of the investigated antiepileptic drugs (valproate, carbamazepine, or levetiracetam), collection of a pre-dose (trough) blood sample, age ≥ 18 years, and two serum concentration measurements. Patients were excluded if these criteria were not met.

Ethics approval

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the Ethics Committee of the University Hospital in Nitra, Slovak Republic. The Ethics Committee operates in compliance with ICH GCP 135/95 and applicable laws and regulations.

Data collection

The following variables were extracted: demographic and anthropometric data (weight, height, and calculated body mass index [BMI]); patient status (inpatient or outpatient); diagnosis; the specific antiepileptic drug monitored; measured drug concentration; total daily dose; calculated weight-adjusted daily dose; dosing interval; any adjustments in daily dosing; and concomitant pharmacotherapy.

For further analysis, the first measurement was designated as C1 and the subsequent measurement as C2. For each patient, the interval between measurements, any dose or dosing interval modifications, and any interventions by a clinical pharmacist were also evaluated. A total of 78 patients met all inclusion criteria: 44 received valproate, 18 received carbamazepine, and 16 received levetiracetam.

Recommended reference ranges for therapeutic concentrations of monitored AEDs

The recommended therapeutic reference ranges for serum concentrations are 50–100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for valproate, 4–12 mg/L for carbamazepine, and 12–46 mg/L for levetiracetam (Patsalos et al. 2018). The dosing regimens for valproate, carbamazepine, and levetiracetam are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Dosing regimens of individual AEDs.

AED	Initial dose	Maintenance dose	Maximum dose
Valproate	10–15 mg/kg/day	20–30 mg/kg/day	60 mg/kg/day
Carbamazepine	100–200 mg once or twice daily	400 mg twice daily	1600 mg daily
Levetiracetam	500 mg twice daily	500–1500 mg twice daily	1500 mg twice daily

Abbreviations: AEDs – antiepileptic drugs.

Based on the measured drug concentrations, patients were classified into the following categories: a) patients with concentrations within the therapeutic range, b) patients with subtherapeutic concentrations, and c) patients with supratherapeutic concentrations.

The stability of treatment

Treatment was considered stable when both the first (C1) and second (C2) serum concentration measurements fell within the established therapeutic range. A categorical variable was assigned: 1 if the treatment remained stable throughout the study and 0 if it did not.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS software, version 19 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Results are presented as absolute numbers, means with standard deviations (mean \pm SD), medians with ranges (minimum–maximum), or percentages, as appropriate. To compare continuous variables, both paired and unpaired t-tests were employed depending on the data structure. All tests were two-tailed, and assumptions for each statistical method were verified prior to analysis. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used for comparisons involving more than two groups.

Spearman's correlation was used to describe the relationship between the daily doses of AEDs and their serum concentration levels. The strength of Spearman's correlation was interpreted as follows: 0.00–0.19 = very weak; 0.20–0.39 = weak; 0.40–0.59 = moderate; 0.60–0.79 = strong; 0.80–1.0 = very strong ($p < 0.05$).

Pearson's chi-square test was used to compare the distribution of categorical variables between stable and unstable treatment groups to assess treatment stability.

To identify significant predictors of treatment stability, a logistic regression model was employed, including the following covariates: basic patient characteristics (age, gender, and BMI); the interval in days between the first (C1) and second (C2) serum concentration measurements; clinical variables such as diagnosis category (F/G/other); treatment setting (outpatient vs. inpatient); and the type of AED used. Model fit was assessed using Nagelkerke's R^2 and the Hosmer–Lemeshow goodness-of-fit test. Results are reported as regression coefficients (b), standard errors (SE), and odds ratios (OR) with corresponding 95% confidence intervals (CIs).

The AI technology *Perplexity* was used to improve word processing and language. No AI-generated content, data analysis, or scientific interpretation was included in the study.

Results

General characteristics of the patients

The analyzed dataset comprised information extracted from laboratory request forms of 78 patients with exactly two serum concentration measurements of one of the following AEDs: valproic acid, carbamazepine, or levetiracetam, recorded within a one-year period. All patients were undergoing long-term therapy with at least one of these agents. The mean age of the study population was 48.58 ± 1.9 years [20–90 years]. The majority of patients were male (64.10%), while females accounted for 35.90% of the cohort. The mean body mass index (BMI) was 29.44 ± 0.80 kg/m² [18.36–52.89 kg/m²], corresponding to the classification of overweight according to CDC criteria (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention 2022). Patients treated with levetiracetam had a significantly lower BMI compared to those receiving valproate (26.54 ± 2.46 vs. 31.38 ± 1.10 ; $p = 0.016$).

At the time of therapeutic drug monitoring, patients were either hospitalized or treated on an outpatient basis at the University Hospital in Nitra, Slovak Republic. Hospitalized patients comprised 82.05% of the cohort, while 17.95% were outpatients. A total of 83.3% of patients had a diagnosed neurological or psychiatric disorder. Table 2 provides a detailed overview of the patients' demographic and clinical characteristics.

Serum concentrations of monitored AEDs

The time interval between C1 and C2 was shortest in patients treated with levetiracetam (8.06 ± 2.46 days), compared to those treated with valproate (25.41 ± 3.43 days; $p = 0.560$) and carbamazepine (206.67 ± 49.53 days; $p < 0.001$).

No statistically significant differences were observed in dosing or serum concentrations of the monitored drugs between the first (C1) and second (C2) measurements. The mean daily dose at the time of the first measurement was 1002.27 mg [300–1750 mg] for valproate, 561.76 mg [150–1050 mg] for carbamazepine, and 1843.75 mg [1000–3000 mg] for levetiracetam. Additional data on dosing and serum concentrations of the individual drugs are provided in Table 3.

Fig. 1 depicts the percentage distribution of subtherapeutic, therapeutic, and supratherapeutic serum concentrations across both controls. On the first control (C1), the majority of carbamazepine concentrations (66.7%) fell within the therapeutic range, compared to 40.9% for valproate and 37.5% for levetiracetam. On the second control (C2), all carbamazepine-treated patients had concentrations within the therapeutic range, whereas 64%

Table 2. Demographic and clinical characteristics of patients.

Parameters	Unit	Valproate	Carbamazepine	Levetiracetam
		n = 44 patients	n = 18 patients	n = 16 patients
Gender (Fe/Ma)	N	13/31	9/9	6/10
	%	29.5/70.5	50/50	37.5/62.5
Enrollment (hosp/amb)	N	43/1	6/12	15/1
	%	97.7/2.3	33.3/66.7	93.8/6.3
Diagnosis (F/G/O)	N	42/0/2	11/6/1	0/6/10
	%	95.5/0/4.5	61.1/33.3/5.6	0/37.5/62.5
Age	Years	42.95 ± 2.21	51.67 ± 3.96	60.56 ± 3.92
	[min-max]	[20-77]	[20-74]	[30-90]
patients<65y/ patients>65y	N	40/4	13/5	10/6
	%	90.9/9.1	72.2/27.8	62.5/37.5
BMI	kg/m ²	31.38 ± 1.09	26.99 ± 1.66	26.54 ± 1.06
	[min-max]	[20.09-52.89]	[18.36-44.24]	[19.53-34.6]
Time interval	days	25.41 ± 3.43	206.67 ± 49.53	8.06 ± 2.46
	[min-max]	[2-109]	[6-604]	[1-34]

Abbreviations: Fe – female; Ma – male; F – psychiatric diagnosis; G – neurological diagnosis; O – other diagnosis; BMI – body mass index.

Table 3. Summary of dosing and serum concentrations of antiepileptic drugs.

	Parameters	Unit	C1	C2	p-value
Valproate	Daily dose	mg	1002.27	1062.50	0.085
		[min-max]	[300-1750]	[500-1750]	
	Median	mg	1000	1000	
	Dose per kg	mg/kg	11.32 ± 0.73	12.02 ± 0.68	0.116
		[min-max]	[4.13-23.33]	[3.94-23.44]	
	Median	mg/kg	10.71	10.93	
Concentration	mg/l	60.45 ± 4.22	59.30 ± 3.23	0.742	
	[min-max]	[8.7-116]	[17.10-110.8]		
Carbamazepine	Daily Dose	mg	561.76	567.65	0.920
		[min-max]	[150-1050]	[150-1050]	
	Median	mg	600	600	
	Dose per kg	mg/kg	7.57	7.86	0.712
		[min-max]	[1.43-12.77]	[2.83-17.31]	
	Median	mg/kg	8.108	6.25	
Concentration	mg/l	7.22	6.81	0.575	
	[min-max]	[2.8-13.60]	[4-9.7]		
Levetiracetam	Daily dose	mg	1843.75	1875.00	0.806
		[min-max]	[1000-3000]	[1000-3000]	
	Median	mg	2000	2000	
	Dose per kg	mg/kg	25.095	25.01	0.563
		[min-max]	[12.5-60]	[15-50]	
	Median	mg/kg	23.53	23.52	
Concentration	mg/l	31.19	28.86	0.966	
	[min-max]	[0.06-101.9]	[6.74-62.25]		

Abbreviations: C1 – first control; C2 – second control.

of valproate – and 50% of levetiracetam-treated patients achieved therapeutic levels.

At C1, a positive relationship was observed between daily dose and serum concentration for both valproate ($\rho = 0.425, p < 0.01$) and carbamazepine ($\rho = 0.712, p < 0.01$). At C2, this relationship remained significant only in the carbamazepine group ($\rho = 0.551, p < 0.05$).

Figure 1. Concentration of antiepileptic drugs within the therapeutic range at control 1 (C1) and control 2 (C2).

Assessment of predictors for treatment stability

Treatment was considered stable when both C1 and C2 serum concentration measurements fell within the established therapeutic range. According to this criterion, the highest treatment stability was observed in patients receiving carbamazepine (66.7%, $\chi^2 = 2.000, p = 0.134$), followed by those treated with valproate (34.1%, $\chi^2 = 4.455, p < 0.05$) and levetiracetam (31.3%, $\chi^2 = 2.250, p = 0.134$).

Based on the results of regression analysis (Table 4), the only factors significantly associated with treatment stability were the number of days between C1 and C2 (OR 1.007, 95% CI: 1.001-1.012, $p = 0.026$), outpatient status (OR 9.132, 95% CI: 1.890-29.817, $p < 0.05$), and treatment with carbamazepine (OR 4.400, 95% CI: 1.041-18.599, $p < 0.05$).

Discussion

Therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM) individualizes pharmacotherapy by measuring serum drug levels to optimize efficacy, minimize toxicity, and assess adherence (De Rosa

Table 4. Results of logistic regression analysis showing odds ratios for treatment stability.

Covariates	b	SE	OR	95% CI	p-value
Age	-0.007	0.016	0.993	0.963–1.025	0.677
Gender [†]	-0.459	0.529	0.632	0.224–1.781	0.385
BMI	0.001	0.035	1.001	0.935–1.072	0.609
Number of days between C1 and C2	0.007	0.003	1.007	1.001–1.012	0.026
Diagnosis F [*]	0.772	1.045	2.164	0.279–16.766	0.460
Diagnosis D [*]	-0.454	1.049	0.635	0.081–4.962	0.665
Outpatients ^{**}	2.212	1.102	9.132	1.890–29.817	0.045
Valproate ^{***}	0.129	0.626	1.138	0.334–3.882	0.837
Carbamazepine ^{***}	1.482	0.735	4.400	1.041–18.599	0.044

Abbreviations: [†]compared to women, ^{*}compared to diagnosis “other,” ^{**}compared to inpatients, ^{***}compared to levetiracetam.

et al. 2023). Due to their narrow therapeutic windows and marked interindividual pharmacokinetic variability, antiepileptic drugs (AEDs) require close monitoring to ensure safe and effective therapy. Consequently, AEDs are among the most frequently monitored drug classes in clinical practice. Indications for TDM typically include treatment initiation, dose adjustments, suspected toxicity or subtherapeutic response, and concerns about patient compliance (Johannessen Landmark et al. 2020; Shawahna et al. 2020).

This study analyzed TDM results for valproate, levetiracetam, and carbamazepine in 78 adults receiving long-term therapy at the University Hospital in Nitra (2020–2022), each with two serum concentration measurements. The time interval between the first (C1) and second (C2) measurements was shortest in patients treated with levetiracetam (approximately 8 days), compared to valproate (about 25 days; $p = 0.560$) and carbamazepine (around 207 days; $p < 0.001$). No significant differences in dosing or serum concentrations were observed between C1 and C2 for any of the drugs. The mean daily doses at C1 were approximately 1,000 mg for valproate, 560 mg for carbamazepine, and 1,840 mg for levetiracetam.

Patients treated with valproate were younger than those receiving levetiracetam ($p < 0.01$) and were predominantly treated for psychiatric disorders, primarily alcohol-related disorders (F10) and schizophrenia (F20). Valproate’s adjunctive use in psychiatric conditions is supported by evidence indicating reductions in aggression and mood symptoms (Wang et al. 2016; Hartz et al. 2014; Salloum et al. 2005). Valproate-associated weight gain, likely mediated by effects on leptin and serotonin, was reflected in the higher BMI of these patients (Kanemura et al. 2012; Petty et al. 2014).

In our study, at the beginning of monitoring (C1), 41% of valproate-treated patients had therapeutic serum levels, 46% were subtherapeutic, and 14% were suprathreshold. At C2, 64% achieved therapeutic levels. Treatment stability in valproate-treated patients was lower than that in those receiving carbamazepine (34% vs. 67%), likely reflecting valproate’s greater pharmacokinetic variability and the influence of comorbidities, drug interactions, and adherence.

Carbamazepine, a first-generation AED, is widely used in epilepsy management, with a recommended therapeutic

serum concentration range of 4–12 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (Aldaz et al. 2011). TDM is essential due to its narrow therapeutic window, variable pharmacokinetics, and potential for toxicity. Large retrospective studies have reported that only 70–73% of patients maintain carbamazepine levels within the therapeutic range, with subtherapeutic or suprathreshold levels in about 25% of cases (Grzešek et al. 2021). Younger patients (aged 3–17 years) tend to maintain therapeutic levels more consistently, despite receiving higher weight-adjusted doses, while adults are more susceptible to overdose and toxicity (Pozzi et al. 2016).

Dosing frequency significantly impacts serum carbamazepine stability. Patients receiving multiple daily doses (two or three times daily) achieve therapeutic concentrations more consistently (72.5–79%) than those on once-daily regimens, where only about 45.5% maintain therapeutic levels (Shakya et al. 2008; Grzešek et al. 2021). This aligns with our findings, where 67% of patients had stable carbamazepine levels, and unstable concentrations were more frequent among those receiving once-daily dosing. The mean daily dose in our cohort (~562 mg) and weight-adjusted dose (~7.7 mg/kg) were somewhat lower than those reported in other studies, potentially contributing to the serum level distribution. At C1, 67% of carbamazepine concentrations were within the therapeutic range, and at C2, all patients had therapeutic levels. Treatment stability was highest for carbamazepine (67%), compared to valproate (34%) and levetiracetam (31%). The long interval between measurements for carbamazepine (>200 days) may reflect clinical confidence in its stability under appropriate dosing regimens, but it also highlights the importance of periodic reassessment due to potential pharmacokinetic changes, drug interactions, or adherence issues.

Levetiracetam, in contrast, demonstrates more predictable pharmacokinetics, with minimal hepatic metabolism and low protein binding, resulting in fewer clinically relevant drug interactions (Patsalos 2004). In our cohort, levetiracetam-treated patients were primarily outpatients with epilepsy. Their mean serum concentrations (C1: 31.19 mg/L; C2: 28.86 mg/L) were higher than those reported in some international studies (May et al. 2003; Ha et al. 2021) but were consistent with Australian data (Stepanova and Beran 2014). This variation likely reflects differences in therapeutic reference ranges, which internationally vary from 10–40 mg/L to 20–40 mg/L (Stepanova and Beran 2014; Ha et al. 2021). The short interval between measurements (8 days) likely reflects clinical scenarios such as recent dose initiation or adjustment or the need to quickly assess adherence or response. Despite pharmacokinetic advantages, only 37.5% of patients had therapeutic levels at C1 and 50% at C2, with overall treatment stability observed in 31.3%. This variability underscores the need for individualized monitoring, even for newer AEDs, particularly when response or adherence is uncertain.

Across all groups, no significant changes in dosing or drug concentrations were observed between C1 and C2, suggesting that routine monitoring alone, within the observed timeframe, did not prompt major therapeutic adjustments. However, the differences in treatment stability

and therapeutic range attainment emphasize the continued need for individualized TDM, especially in the context of clinical change, suspected nonadherence, or polypharmacy.

Relevant drug interactions observed included reduced valproate levels in the presence of CYP inducers such as phenytoin and increased levels with CYP2C9 inhibitors like fluconazole. Carbamazepine patients were exposed to CYP3A4 inhibitors, including ciprofloxacin, fluconazole, and linagliptin. Co-administration of valproate and carbamazepine may influence plasma concentrations due to opposing metabolic effects (Patel and Anilkumar 2025). No significant interactions were noted with levetiracetam, consistent with its limited hepatic metabolism.

Adherence remains critical for seizure control. Common barriers include forgetfulness, prolonged seizure-free periods, fear of adverse effects, and limited understanding of the treatment regimen (Tang et al. 2013). Healthcare professionals play a crucial role in improving adherence through patient education, clear communication, and comprehensive medication reviews to identify drug-related problems and simplify regimens.

Together, these findings highlight that while carbamazepine requires careful dose adjustment and frequent TDM—particularly with respect to dosing frequency and patient age—levetiracetam offers a more stable pharmacokinetic profile with fewer concerns regarding drug interactions. Nonetheless, regular monitoring remains essential to ensure optimal seizure control and patient safety.

It is important to acknowledge certain limitations of this study. It was retrospective, based on existing medical records, and did not directly assess patient adherence—a key determinant of serum drug levels. Additionally, renal and hepatic function data were not evaluated, and there was variability in the time intervals between the two serum measurements. The relatively small sample size and single-center setting further limit the generalizability of the findings. Nonetheless, the study has notable strengths, including the use of real-world clinical data, a comparative analysis of three commonly prescribed AEDs, and a clear emphasis on the role of TDM in optimizing pharmacotherapy.

Conclusion

In summary, our findings reinforce that carbamazepine can achieve high treatment stability when appropriate dosing regimens and periodic monitoring are applied. Levetiracetam, despite its favorable pharmacokinetics, also benefits from individualized therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM) in selected cases. The variability observed with valproate further supports the importance of regular monitoring, particularly in complex patient populations. These results are consistent with current guidelines, which recommend TDM as a complementary tool in specific clinical contexts to optimize seizure control and minimize adverse effects. When determining and adjusting the dosing of antiepileptic or other narrow-therapeutic-index

drugs, it is essential to consider individual patient characteristics, including demographic, anthropometric, and clinical factors—such as the primary diagnosis, comorbid conditions, and concomitant pharmacotherapy.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

We confirmed that the study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the Ethics Committee of the University Hospital in Nitra, Slovak Republic. The Ethics Committee operates according to the ICH GCP 135/95 request and the applicable laws and regulations.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the patients participating in the study. The Ethics Committee of the University Hospital in Nitra, Slovak Republic, has confirmed that informed consent to participate is not required in view of the retrospective nature of the study. All data were anonymized by institution, and the submission does not include any data that may identify the person. The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

Use of AI

The AI technology Perplexity was used to improve word processing and language. No AI-generated content, data analysis, or scientific interpretation was included in the study.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization and methodology L.Ž., M.G., S.K.; software L.Ž., A.G., O.H., S.K.; formal analysis L.Ž., S.K.; investigation L.Ž., M.G.; writing—original draft preparation L.Ž., S.K.; writing—review and editing M.G., O.H., A.G. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data availability

Data that support the findings of this study are available upon reasonable request from the corresponding author [S.K.].

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